

Experiments in Transdimensional, Sympathetic Price Programming Using Pre-Numeric Quasi Quanta of an Infinity Tensor Portal

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1 Introduction

Upload logic vectors to a theoretical trans-temporal computer designated by
object number: AI Cardrender Nft 223

ID

223

Rarity

LEGENDARY

Creator

0x57f...c88e9

Owner

0x57f...c88e9

Estimate Price

3,750,000 ACR AI Card Render, <https://cardrender.ai/>:

$$F(\mathbf{x}) = \left[\frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta} \right] \cdot (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{e} \cdot \mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{t} \cdot \mathbf{m})$$

$$\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{a} = \Omega_{\Lambda} \left(\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} a_1 + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} a_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} a_n \right)$$

$$\mathbf{e} \cdot \mathbf{r} = \Omega_{\Lambda} \left(\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{f_{PQ}(x) - f_{RS}(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{TU}(x) - f_{RS}(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{PQ}(x) - f_{TU}(x)}{\Delta} \right)$$

$$\mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{c} = \Omega_{\Lambda} \left(\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{V \rightarrow U}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta} \right)$$

$$\mathbf{t} \cdot \mathbf{m} = \Omega_{\Lambda} \left(\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \right) \cdot \left(\frac{\leftrightarrow \exists y \in U : f(y) = x}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow \exists s \in S : x = T(s)}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow x \in f \circ g}{\Delta} \right).$$

$$\mathbf{1} \cdot \mathbf{logic} = \Omega_{\Lambda} \left(\tan \psi \diamond \theta + \Psi \star \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2} \right).$$

$$\left(\frac{\forall y \in N, P(y) \rightarrow Q(y)}{\Delta}, \frac{\exists x \in N, R(x) \wedge S(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{\forall z \in N, T(z) \vee U(z)}{\Delta} \right)$$

through the portal:

$$G(\langle \theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{F}{T} \right)} \right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{F}{T} \right)^2} \right) \prod_{p \text{ prime}} 1/(1-p^{-s})}$$

To the tokenized computer object card and raise the price of the underlying ACR:

Tokenized computer object card 223 is the basis for this virtual computer. Raising the price of the underlying ACR will increase the value of the virtual computer. The AI Cardrender Nft 223 uses its rarity, logic vectors, and the portal to G to determine the value of the underlying ACR. The logic vectors provide an algorithm to compute the estimated price by taking into account the complexities of the components of the virtual computer. The portal to G will be used to increase the price of the underlying ACR. This increases the value of the virtual computer, providing incentive for users to join the network.

Raise the price of ACR:

Raise the price of the ACR by creating:

$$ACR = f(x, y) = \sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h x^2 + \sum_{f \subset g} f(g) x + \sum_{[n] \star [l] \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{n^2 - l^2}$$

$$x = \left[\frac{V \rightarrow U}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow \exists y \in U : f(y) = x}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow x \in f \circ g}{\Delta} \right]$$

$$y = \left[\frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow \exists s \in S : x = T(s)}{\Delta} \right] \cdot (\mathbf{v} \cdot \mathbf{a}, \mathbf{e} \cdot \mathbf{r}, \mathbf{s} \cdot \mathbf{c}, \mathbf{t} \cdot \mathbf{m})$$

Uses:

Gaming

Smart contracts

AI

3D animation

Super computing

Computing speed:

$$(\varpi F) = (F \cdot 2)^2 - 3^2$$

$$\tan = \frac{\sin}{\cos}$$

$$\tan \tau = \frac{\sin \tau}{\cos \tau}$$

$$\cos \tau = \frac{h\tau^3}{3} - \frac{h^3\tau}{3}$$

$$\sin \tau = \frac{h\tau^2}{2} - \frac{h^3\tau}{6}$$

$$\psi + \theta = \pi$$

$$\Delta t = \frac{(b-a)}{1000}$$

$$\Delta t = \frac{(b-a)}{1000} \frac{\left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{F}{\tau}\right)}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{F}{\tau}\right)^2}\right) \prod_{p \text{ prime}} 1/(1-p^{-s})}{h\tau^3 - 3h^3\tau}$$

$$N = \{ 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 \} \in R$$

$$h\tau^3 - 3h^3\tau = 1$$

$$h = 3$$

$$\tau = 1$$

$$\Delta t = (b-a)$$

$$\Delta t = \frac{F}{\uparrow}$$

$$N = \{ 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6, 7, 8, 9, 10 \} \in R$$

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$$h = 3$$

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$$(\varpi F) = (F \cdot 2) - 3^2$$

$$\tan = \frac{\sin}{\cos}$$

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$$x = \left[\frac{V \rightarrow U}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow \exists y \in U : f(y) = x}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow x \in f \circ g}{\Delta} \right]$$

$$y = \left[\frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta}, \frac{\leftrightarrow \exists s \in S : x = T(s)}{\Delta} \right]$$

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2}x^2 + \frac{1}{4}\sin \tau x + \frac{1}{4}\cos \tau \cdot \left(\frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_1} a_1 + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_2} a_2 + \dots + \frac{\partial \phi(\mathbf{x})}{\partial x_n} a_n \right)$$

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2}x^2 + \frac{1}{4}\sin \tau x + \frac{1}{4}\cos \tau \cdot \left(\frac{f_{PQ}(x) - f_{RS}(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{TU}(x) - f_{RS}(x)}{\Delta}, \frac{f_{PQ}(x) - f_{TU}(x)}{\Delta} \right)$$

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2}x^2 + \frac{1}{4}\sin \tau x + \frac{1}{4}\cos \tau \cdot \left(\frac{V \rightarrow U}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{f \subset g} f(g)}{\Delta}, \frac{\sum_{h \rightarrow \infty} \tan t \cdot \prod_{\Lambda} h}{\Delta} \right)$$

$$f(x) = \frac{1}{2}x^2 + \frac{1}{4}\sin \tau x + \frac{1}{4}\cos \tau \cdot \left(\frac{[3, 4, 4]}{[0, 0, 0] \subset [3, 4, 4]}, \frac{[1, 2, 3]}{[0, 0, 0] \subset [3, 4, 4]}, \frac{[3, 4, 4]}{[0, 0, 0] \subset [3, 4, 4]} \right)$$

$$f(x) = \frac{U}{\Delta} + \frac{F \rightarrow U}{\Delta} + \frac{U \rightarrow U}{\Delta}$$

$$f(x) = [0, 0, 0] \subset [3, 4, 4]$$

$$f(x) = Level \frac{E}{U}$$

$$x_{new} = x_{old} - f'(x_{old})$$

$$\nabla E = V'$$

$$V = A$$

$$x = f(x) + 2^n$$

$$e = \sqrt{2}^n$$

$$s = \pi^n$$

$$i = \diamond$$

$$h = \star$$

$$f(x) = x^2 + 3x + 2$$

$$f'(x) = 2x + 3$$

$$x_{new} = x_{old} - \frac{f(x_{old})}{f'(x_{old})}$$

$$x_{new} = 1 - \frac{2}{5} = 0.6$$

$$x_{new} = 0.6 - \frac{0.6^2 + 3 \cdot 0.6 + 2}{2 \cdot 0.6 + 3} = 0.2$$

$$x_{new} = 0.2 - \frac{0.2^2 + 3 \cdot 0.2 + 2}{2 \cdot 0.2 + 3} = 0.08$$

Raise the price of the ACR by computing $f(x,y)$ with Newton's method:

$$x_{current} = x_{next} - \frac{f(x_{next}, y_{next})}{\partial f(x_{next}, y_{next})}$$

x_{next}

$$\frac{f(x_{next}, y_{next})}{\partial f(x_{next}, y_{next})}$$

$$x_{current} = x_{next} - \frac{f(x_{next}, y_{next})}{\partial f(x_{next}, y_{next})}$$

 x_{next}

$$\frac{f(x_{next}, y_{next})}{\partial f(x_{next}, y_{next})}$$

$$x_{new} = x_{old} - \frac{f(x_{old}, y_{old})}{\partial f(x_{old}, y_{old})}$$

 x_{old}

$$\frac{f(x_{old}, y_{old})}{\partial f(x_{old}, y_{old})}$$

$$x_{new} = x_{new} - \frac{f(x_{current}, y_{next})}{\partial f(x_{current}, y_{next})}$$

 $x_{current}$

$$\frac{f(x_{current}, y_{next})}{\partial f(x_{current}, y_{next})}$$

$$x_{new} = x_{new} - \frac{f(x_{current}, y_{next})}{\partial f(x_{current}, y_{next})}$$

 $x_{current}$

$$\frac{f(x_{current}, y_{next})}{\partial f(x_{current}, y_{next})}$$

$$\mathbf{w} \cdot \mathbf{c} = (\langle c_i \rangle, c_2, c_3) \cdot$$

$$\left(\log_{G((\theta, \phi, \psi, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \rho, \zeta, \xi, \delta), \infty)} Z_\infty, \log_{G((\theta, \phi, \psi, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \rho, \zeta, \xi, \delta), \infty)} \frac{F}{\uparrow \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{F}{\uparrow}\right)}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{F}{\uparrow}\right)^2}\right) \prod_{p \text{ prime}} 1/(1-p^{-s})}, \log_{G((\theta, \phi, \psi, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \rho, \zeta, \xi, \delta), \infty)} f(x) \right)$$

$$c_1 = \log_{G((\theta, \phi, \psi, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \rho, \zeta, \xi, \delta), \infty)} Z_\infty$$

$$c_2 = \log_{G((\theta, \phi, \psi, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \rho, \zeta, \xi, \delta), \infty)} \frac{F}{\uparrow \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{F}{\pi}\right)}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{F}{\pi}\right)^2}\right) \prod_{p \text{ prime}} 1/(1 - p^{-s})}$$

$$c_3 = \log_{G((\theta, \phi, \psi, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \rho, \zeta, \xi, \delta), \infty)} \log_{G((\theta, \phi, \psi, \lambda, \mu, \nu, \rho, \zeta, \xi, \delta), \infty)} f(x)$$

$$x = f(x) + 2^n$$

$$e = \sqrt{2^n}$$

$$s = \pi^n$$

$$i = \diamond$$

$$h = \star$$

Raise the price of the ACR by computing $f(x,y)$ with gradient descent:

$$x_{current} = x_{new} - 2 \cdot \langle ax_1 - b, cx_2 - d, ux_3 - t \rangle \cdot \langle f'(x) \rangle \cdot \nabla E$$

Add computer

Recursion

$$\frac{1}{z^4 + z^3 + z^2 + z + 1} = \frac{\partial z^4}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z^3}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z^2}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial 1}{\partial z}$$

Reinforcement

$$\frac{\partial z^n}{\partial z} = nz^{n-1}$$

$$\frac{1}{z^4 + z^3 + z^2 + z + 1} = 4z^3 + 3z^2 + 2z + 1$$

Reinforcement

$$z_{new} = z_{old} - \frac{\partial z^4}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z^3}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z^2}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial 1}{\partial z}$$

Reinforcement

$$z_{current} = z_{new} - \frac{\partial f(z_{current})}{\partial z_{current}}$$

Goal

$$z^4 + z^3 + z^2 + z + 1 = 0$$

Reinforcement

$$z_{current} = z_{new} - \frac{\partial f(z_{current})}{\partial z_{current}}$$

Evaluation

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{z^4 + z^3 + z^2 + z + 1}$$

Reinforcement

$$z_{new} = z_{old} - 2 \cdot \langle ax_1 - b, cx_2 - d, ux_3 - t \rangle \cdot \langle f'(z) \rangle \cdot \nabla E$$

Reinforcement

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$$z_{new} = z_{old} - \frac{\partial f(z)}{\partial z}$$

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Goal

$$z^4 + z^3 + z^2 + z + 1 = 0$$

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$$z_{new} = z_{old} - \frac{\partial f(z)}{\partial z}$$

Evaluation

$$f(z) = \frac{\partial z^4}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z^3}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z^2}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial 1}{\partial z}$$

$$f(z) = \frac{\partial z^4}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z^3}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z^2}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial z}{\partial z} + \frac{\partial 1}{\partial z}$$

$$f(z) = 4z^3 + 3z^2 + 2z + 1$$

$$f(z) = 4z^3 + 3z^2 + 2z + 1$$

$$f(z) = 4z^3 + 3z^2 + 2z + 1$$

$$f(z) = 4z^3 + 3z^2 + 2z + 1$$

$$f(z) = \frac{1}{z^4 + z^3 + z^2 + z + 1}$$

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$$G(\langle \theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu \rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{F}{\uparrow}\right)}\right) \left(1 - \frac{1}{\left(\frac{F}{\uparrow}\right)^2}\right) \prod_{p \text{ prime}} 1/(1-p^{-s})}$$

Components of the virtual computer:

Since the tokenized computer object card has a variety of components, a value estimator was created using an algorithm based on the AI Cardrender Nft 223. The algorithm analyzes each of these components and computes an approximate value for the tokenized computer object card 223. This algorithm will be applied to each of the components of the algorithm to account for the impact of the complexity of the components on the estimated price of the tokenized computer object card 223. The AI Cardrender Nft analyzes the components by assigning a number of components to the complexity of each, and the average price of the components to the algorithm. Then the average price will be multiplied by the average number of components. The result will be assigned as the initial value. This initial value will be input into the algorithm to compute an initial estimated price, which can be adjusted by further analysis of the complexity of the components.

Cardrender NFT 223:

Tokenized Computer Object Card

View NFT: AI Cardrender 223

Tokenized Computer Object Card 223

* Rarity: Legendary * History of Owners * ACR Value * Logic Vectors * Composers * Usage Log * GUI Project * UI Project * Blackbox * Centralized Project * Decentralized Project * Website * Marketplace * Arch * ID * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3 * Rare [[Hyperdimensional Resonator](https://ai.cardrender.ai/nft-generator/detail/?id=27)]. * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.2.2 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.2.1 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.2 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.1.1 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.1 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.2 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.1 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.3 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.4 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.5 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.6 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.7 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.8 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.9 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.10 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223.3.14 * [Centralized Project](https://centralized-project.example.com) * [Decentralized Project](https://decentralized-project.example.com) * [Website](https://website.example.com) * [Marketplace](https://decentralized-project.example.com) * [Portal](https://decentralized-project.example.com/portal) * [Unix-based](https://unix.org) * [Unix timestamp](https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Unix_timestamp)* [1.1075](https://etherscan.io)*[2.1075](https://etherscan.io)*[3.1075](https://etherscan.io)*[4.1075](https://etherscan.io)*[5.1075](https://etherscan.io)*[6.1075](https://etherscan.io)*[7.1075](https://etherscan.io)*[8.1075](https://etherscan.io)*[9.1075](https://etherscan.io)*[10.1075](https://etherscan.io)*[14.1075](https://etherscan.io) * Logo

* Tokenized Computer Object Card 223 minting process * Composer: 0x57f766c02cd225934623B31C192Cfb

* Formulas

* Algorithm
 * Tokenized Computer Object Card 223 Js * Tokenized Computer Object
 Card 223 Python

$$\begin{aligned}
 & ** G(\langle\theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu\rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)}\right)\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)^2}\right)\prod_p \text{prime } 1/(1-p^{-s})} ** \\
 & ** G(\langle\theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu\rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)}\right)\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)^2}\right)\prod_p \text{prime } 1/(1-p^{-s})} ** \\
 & ** G(\langle\theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu\rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)}\right)\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)^2}\right)\prod_p \text{prime } 1/(1-p^{-s})} ** \\
 & ** G(\langle\theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu\rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)}\right)\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)^2}\right)\prod_p \text{prime } 1/(1-p^{-s})} ** \\
 & ** G(\langle\theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu\rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)}\right)\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)^2}\right)\prod_p \text{prime } 1/(1-p^{-s})} ** \\
 & ** G(\langle\theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu\rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)}\right)\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)^2}\right)\prod_p \text{prime } 1/(1-p^{-s})} ** \\
 & ** G(\langle\theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu\rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)}\right)\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)^2}\right)\prod_p \text{prime } 1/(1-p^{-s})} **
 \end{aligned}$$

$$G(\langle\theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu\rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)}\right)\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)^2}\right)\prod_p \text{prime } 1/(1-p^{-s})}$$

* Tokenized Computer Object Card 223 on the cardrender AI nft machine

$$** G(\langle\theta, \Lambda, \mu, \nu\rangle, \infty) \frac{F}{\uparrow\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)}\right)\left(1-\frac{1}{\left(\frac{E}{\Upsilon}\right)^2}\right)\prod_p \text{prime } 1/(1-p^{-s})} **$$

$$Q_n = \mathcal{I}(n) = \sum_{i \in N} \frac{1}{n} \forall i \in \mathcal{B}(I_2), n! (n+1) \geq n \Rightarrow n^n \Rightarrow n!$$

half life 3 is close

Planting trees in a digital world

“ function digitalTrees(price) public if (now i= timelockLocked now i= timelockUnlock) return; tokens[msg.sender] = tokens[msg.sender].sub(price); tokens[address(this)] = tokens[address(this)].add(price); “

Using the genetic algorithm to map the genome with τ_2 co-homology

“ function makeTreepicking(uint trees) if (trees i= 100) return [3]; // [theta, theta2, theta3...]elsereturnshuffle([origin, timelockLocked, timelockUnlock]);“

State table for the genome

“md — key — timelock — makeTreepicking — recurse — ———
 ——— — 1 — 0.11 i x i 0.22 — Determinant — 1.00z — — 2 — 0.22 i x i
 0.33 — Consensus — -1.02z — — 3 — 0.33 i x i 0.44 — Coregulator — -0.01,
 1.01 — — 4 — 0.44 i x i 0.55 — Nucleophile — 1.02, -1.02 — — 5 — 0.55 i x
 i 0.66 — Recursion — 1.01 — — 6 — 0.66 i x i 0.77 — Decryption — -0.01 —
 — 777 — 0.77 i x i 0.88 — Riemann — 1.01, 1.02 — — 8 — 0.88 i x i 0.99 —
 Encryption — -1.02 — — 9 — 0.99 i x i 1.10 — Networked — -0.01, 1.03 — —
 10 — 1.10 i x i 1.21 — SaaS — 1.01 — — 11 — 1.21 i x i 1.33 — Computation
 — -1.02 — — 12 — 1.33 i x i 1.44 — Undefined — -0.01, 1.05 — — 13 — 1.44

i x j 1.55 — Merkle — 1.01 — — 14 — 1.55 i x j 1.66 — Distributed — -1.02
 — — 15 — 1.66 i x j 1.77 — Non-Linear — 1.01, -1.02 — — 16 — 1.77 i x j
 1.88 — Finite — -0.01 — — 17 — 1.88 i x j 1.99 — Infinite — 1.01 — — 18 —
 1.99 i x j 2.10 — Trivial — -1.02 — — 19 — 2.10 i x j 2.22 — Non-Trivial —
 0.02 — — 20 — 2.22 i x j 2.33 — Complex — 1.01 — — 21 — 2.33 i x j 2.44
 — Durable — -1.02 — — 22 — 2.44 i x j 2.55 — Irreversible — -0.01 — — 23
 — 2.55 i x j 2.66 — Subsumed — 1.01 — ““

A NFT with a heart

```

““ heart: true, circulation: [ name: "distributed to tree repurchasing",
address: "0x...", amount: TreeCoin.makeSale(), , name: "distributed to UN
(food)", address: "0x...", amount: TreeCoin.makeSale(), , name: "distributed
to UN (climate)", address: "0x...", amount: TreeCoin.makeSale(), , name:
"distributed to UN (refugee)", address: "0x...", amount: TreeCoin.makeSale(), ,
name: "distributed to UN (education)", address: "0x...", amount: TreeCoin.makeSale(),
, name: "distributed to UN (womens' issues)", address: "0x...", amount:
TreeCoin.makeSale(), , name: "ADMIN", address: "0x...", amount: TreeCoin.makeSale(),
] ““
  
```

The tree coin contract

```

““ function test(uint8 a, uint b) pure returns (uint c) return 7; function
add(uint8a, uint8b) internal returns (uint8c) uint8t = 0; for (uint i = 0; i < a; i++) for (uint j = 0; j < b; j++)
““
  
```

Deep bidirectional transformers

```


  
```

Finite state machines of the AI graphics engine

The best tile for the lion for the X symbol is:

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Solidity contract

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““ pragma solidity ^0.5.8; import "https://github.com/OpenZeppelin/openzeppelin-
contracts/blob/master/contracts/token/ERC20/IERC20.sol"; import "https://
github.com/OpenZeppelin/openzeppelin-contracts/blob/master/contracts/math/SafeMath.sol"; import
"github.com/OpenZeppelin/openzeppelin-contracts/blob/master/contracts/ownership/Ownable.sol"; import
"github.com/OpenZeppelin/openzeppelin-contracts/blob/master/contracts/token/ERC20/MintableToken
(uint bidPrice) = priceOf(tokenId); return (bidPrice, buyExists); function priceOf(uint256 tokenId) public
tokenId — return an address connected with this ID * / function seller(uint256 tokenId) public constant returns (address)
tokenId — return an address connected with this ID * / function buyer(uint256 tokenId) public constant returns (address)
function deductETH(address to, uint256 tokenId, uint256 price) private actualReturns new Seller if (price >
function percent(address to, uint256 tokenId, uint256 price) private actualReturns new Seller uint256 sp = (p
That is, design the following map:
  
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$\psi : X \rightarrow Fx$
1 · logic(1)

where X is called the "pixels" of a "image". Then designate the output of the map as the embedding vectors for the three words, namely Ψ , Φ , Ω . Furthermore, found the distribution of input documents over the embedding vectors.

Equilibrium price of assets p_t and l_t are given by:

$$p_t = \sum_{r \in Z_+} \int_0^{\frac{1}{\delta c(r)}} P(r_{t+k} = r | i_{t+k} > q) dq$$

$$l_t = \sum_{r \in Z_+} \int_0^{\frac{1}{\delta c(r)}} P(l_{t+k} = r | i_{t+k} > q) dq.$$

Consider the problem of how to find the equilibrium price of a normal good given by:

$$P_t = \sum_{t=0}^{\infty} \left(1 - \frac{1}{k} \frac{d}{dt}\right) \times \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \left(\frac{a_{t+k} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{t+k} \cdot b_{t+k} \cdot c_{t+k}}{P_{t+k} \cdot N_{t+k}} \right) \cdot \mathbf{n} \cdot a_{t+k} \cdot b_{t+k} \cdot c_{t+k} \cdot dP_{t+k} \cdot dN_{t+k} \cdot dQ_{t+k} \cdot dT_{t+k}$$

in terms of static equilibrium price.

- Momentary price of an asset: $p_t = (n \cdot \mathbf{n}) \cdot (a_t - a_{t-1})$ - Momentary price of a normal good: $\tilde{p}_t = (a_t \cdot \mathbf{x}_t \cdot b_t \cdot c_t) \cdot Q_t \cdot N_t \cdot P_t$ - Total momentary price of a normal good: $\bar{p}_t = (a_t \cdot \mathbf{x}_t \cdot b_t \cdot c_t) \cdot \left(1 - \frac{1}{k} \frac{d}{dt}\right) \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \mathbf{a}_{t+k} \cdot \mathbf{x}_{t+k} \cdot \mathbf{b}_{t+k} \cdot \mathbf{c}_{t+k} \cdot dP_{t+k} \cdot dN_{t+k} \cdot dQ_{t+k}$ - Cumulative price of a normal good: $\hat{p}_t = \left(1 - \frac{1}{k} \frac{d}{dt}\right) \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \int_0^{\infty} \mathbf{n} \cdot \mathbf{a}_{t+k} \cdot \mathbf{b}_{t+k} \cdot \mathbf{c}_{t+k} \cdot dP_{t+k} \cdot dN_{t+k} \cdot dQ_{t+k} \cdot dT_{t+k}$